

EXCEPTIONS TO THE ASSUMPTION UNDERLYING THE SO-CALLED PHYSICALLY BASED FAILURE THEORIES

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ABSTRACT

This paper re-examines a well-accepted, mostly blindly, assumption adopted in many of modern composites failure criteria. After a brief review of its source, its inapplicability to heterogeneous and anisotropic composites has been argued rationally. As a further reinforcement to the argument made, two exceptions to the assumption have been cited first in the form of thought experiments and followed by physical experiments as the closest resemblances to the idealised thought experiments. In each case, fracture was observed in a plane on which macroscopic stresses vanish completely. The fracture observed cannot be attributed to the stresses exposed on the fracture plane. Any failure criterion based on this assumption is therefore not expected to predict the truthful material failure behaviour in a comprehensive manner. Any claim of the so-called ‘physically based’ criterion because it is based on this particular assumption is fundamentally flawed and therefore cannot be considered as credible. A new and rational approach will have to abandon this assumption before developing a reliable theory.

1 INTRODUCTION

Early attempts of formulating theoretical failure criteria employed a single failure function of stresses involving experimentally determined material’s strength constants. Typical examples were Hoffman [1] and Tsai-Wu [2], to name but a few. Some of these originators categorized failure criteria as purely empirical exercises [3]. Whilst there is a good degree of truth in this description, mindful empiricism should be assisted with rationalism wherever rationalism applies. The endeavour in predicting composites failure took a sharp turn when Hashin proposed his failure criteria [4] where he introduced different failure modes into the consideration. A fundamental assumption adopted to facilitate such partitioning of failure modes was that “**Failure was determined by the stresses exposed on the fracture plane**”, referred to as *Assumption F* hereafter. Since then, those following this line of attack have labelled their approaches as ‘physically based’, e.g. [5,6]. In fact, Hashin did not call his approach ‘physically based’, although he did employ a description as ‘... attractive because of its sound physical basis’. However, this was to describe the introduction of the fracture plane orientation as one of the variables in the failure function for the prediction of matrix failure where reference was made to Mohr. In all fairness, this particular aspect was not particularly physically sound in the Mohr criterion [7,8]. Somehow, the physical soundness has been transplanted to Assumption F Hashin introduced early without mentioning Mohr but in the same paper. It was well-known that the assumption was a part of the criterion named after Mohr. Perhaps, Hashin avoided clarifying the use of this assumption made by Mohr for a good reason, because it was strictly inapplicable to anisotropic materials if one genuinely respects the Mohr criterion [8]. Unfortunately, since Hashin [4], Assumption F has been taken for granted and the failure criteria derived from it have been labelled as *physically based*, implying that it was correct and therefore should not be challenged. This paper is to caution the blind use of this assumption, somehow to go against popularity as if to swim against the tide.

As Assumption F was inherited from the Mohr failure criterion, it will be first reviewed in the context of the Mohr criterion to reveal that its applicability is strictly restricted to isotropic and homogeneous materials. The extension of its use to anisotropic composites is therefore fundamentally flawed.

The objective of the present paper is to present experimental evidences against Assumption F in its applications to heterogeneous and anisotropic composites. Testing of composites is not meant to be simple by all means. To ease the difficulties, the authors will first propose two *thought experiments* (TE) in the same fashion as when Einstein established his special theory of relativity. Arguments will be made to justify the likely modes of failure. The nature of these failure modes would disprove the so-called physically based Assumption F.

To capture the spirit of these TEs, two designated and yet simple enough physical experiments will also be presented. Although they do not reproduce all the features as present in the TEs, they should be sufficient to put the observations made and conclusions drawn from them beyond any reasonable doubt.

2 ASSUMPTION F AND ITS RESTRICTIONS

In the failure of heterogeneous materials, whilst the intention of all phenomenological failure criteria was to address the problem based on macroscopic stresses or strains, the non-uniform distribution of stresses and strains at a lower length scale plays a significant part, where strength is usually dictated by the stresses or strains at the lower length scale, especially for brittle materials. The basic assumption of homogeneity applies only if the average stresses or strains are deemed to be sufficient for the determination of the failure of the material. This is therefore a rather restrictive assumption. Any extension of the Mohr criterion or any of its generic assumptions from commonly accepted homogeneous materials to materials of clear heterogeneity, such as modern fibre-reinforced composites, should not be attempted without appropriate justifications.

The anisotropy of composites is another aspect which deserves sufficient elaboration in relation to the Mohr criterion. The assumption of isotropy in the Mohr criterion allows the material to choose its critical plane to fracture according to the stress state, and the stress state only. Assumption F in the context of the Mohr criterion for isotropic materials can be justified on this basis, which makes the major Mohr's circle representative as far as the failure is concerned. In absence of isotropy, this process of self-identification of the critical plane will no longer apply as the material has relatively stronger and weaker directions due to its anisotropy which is completely independent of the stress state.

In an isotropic material, it is reasonable to envisage that stresses elect the most representative components to cause the fracture and consequently to appear on the fracture plane. This helps to neglect the relatively insignificant contributions from other stress components. When the stress state is expressed in terms of principal stresses, the effects of other stresses making negligible contributions can be encapsulated into the intermediate principal stress. If this self-selection process is interfered by other considerations, such as materials anisotropy, the components exposed on the fracture plane may no longer be as representative as they would otherwise, as far as failure is concerned. The contributions from other stress components would therefore no longer be negligible. Consequently, one can no longer expect the fracture on a plane to be completely determined by the stresses exposed on the plane. The validity of Assumption F for applications to composites is therefore rather questionable, although it has never been challenged in the literature.

Failure should be determined by the stress state, i.e. all stress components, to be universally correct, in general. In the case when it can be determined by some of the components, e.g. when the maximum principal stress, the Tresca, etc. become applicable, these components have to be sufficiently representative. Their representativeness relies on the isotropy of the materials, i.e. the material has the freedom of electing the fracture plane based on the stress state alone. With imposed restriction of anisotropy in dictating the fracture plane, selecting only a few components of the stress state to determine the failure is a pure hypothesis at its best, unsupported and hence vulnerable. The establishment of the Mohr criterion does not offer any support to this hypothesis, except providing the source of the hypothesis, even though it was not explicitly cited in Hashin's original paper [4]. In the meantime, exceptions to the hypothesis can be demonstrated as is the purpose of the present paper. It is therefore high time to reflect Assumption F and its relevance to composite failure criteria if genuine progresses are to be made in this front of science and technology.

3 EXCEPTION 1

The first exception to Assumption F in the context of its applications to heterogeneous and anisotropic composites is associated with the biaxial compression in directions transverse to fibres. An ideal stress state is equal biaxial compression as depicted in Fig. 1

Fig. 1: A stress state of equal biaxial compression transverse to fibres

For this particular stress state, Hashin [4] assumed an infinite strength in order to obtain an additional condition to determine one more constant coefficient in the failure function. This was contradicted when Puck introduced fibre tensile failure criterion [5] as

$$\sigma_1 - \left(\nu_{12} - m_\sigma^f \frac{\nu_{12}^f E_1}{E_1^f} \right) (\sigma_2 + \sigma_3) = \sigma_{1t}^* \quad (1)$$

where E_1 and ν_{12} are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the UD composite in the fibre direction, those with the superscript ' f ' are their counterparts for fibres and σ_{1t}^* is the tensile strength of the composite in the fibre direction. m_σ^f is a so-called stress magnification factor relating the macroscopic transverse stresses to the stresses in the fibres, which is taken as a constant at 1.1~1.3 depending on the properties of the constituents of the composite. In theory, failure could take place even if $\sigma_1 = 0$ when

$$\sigma = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -\sigma_{1t}^* / 2 \left(\nu_{12} - m_\sigma^f \frac{\nu_{12}^f E_1}{E_1^f} \right). \quad (2)$$

3.1 Thought experiment 1: UD composites subjected to equal biaxial transverse compression

Equal biaxial compression is not easy to apply experimentally. A thought experiment is resorted to. Without employing the equations provided above quantitatively, a qualitative argument can be made as follows. The generalised Hooke's law [9] alone is sufficient to tell that the UD composite under equal biaxial compression transverse to fibres would expand in the direction along fibres.

$$\varepsilon_1 = -\frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_2 = -\frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_3. \quad (3)$$

This is the strain in the composites and also the strain fibres have to experience. Fibres are strong against stretching but their capacity is finite. Sooner or later, they would fail. When it eventually took place, it would feature fibre fracture. It would not be too controversial to suggest that the fracture surface is perpendicular to the fibres, although this has never been confirmed precisely through experiments. The failure behaviour as described here can therefore only be presented as a thought experiment conducted in one's mind.

3.2 A physical test close to the above thought experiment

Unlike physicists, engineers may unlikely be content with a thought experiment. A relevant physical test is biaxial transverse compression with slightly unequal stresses in the two directions as a

compromise. Provided that the disparity is properly managed, the failure would still be in fibre tension on the plane perpendicular to fibres, on which macroscopic stresses exposed all vanish. This was achieved by putting a UD composite cube inside a channel within a steel block, see Fig. 2. The UD cube was loaded in one of the transverse directions through a punch into the channel on the top whilst constrained by the walls of the channel in the other transverse direction and the base plate of the testing machine at the bottom of the specimen.

Fig. 2: Steel fixture with a slot for a cubic specimen fitted in the middle (a) drawing and (b) photo

Biaxial compression is generated due to the Poisson's ratio in the transverse direction. Approximating the constraints from the channel wall as rigid, according to the generalized Hooke's law [9], the transverse stress resulting from the Poisson's ratio is

$$\sigma_3 = \nu_{23}\sigma_2 \quad \text{as a result of} \quad \varepsilon_3 = -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2}\sigma_2 + \frac{1}{E_2}\sigma_3 = 0 \quad (4)$$

in absence of σ_1 . The same condition of $\sigma_1=0$ will also lead to

$$\varepsilon_1 = -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2}(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3) = -\frac{\nu_{12}(1 + \nu_{23})}{E_1}\sigma_2. \quad (5)$$

Following the same argument as made in the TE, fibre fracture due to tension will take place sooner or later.

In the above elaboration, the effects of friction between the specimen under testing and its surroundings have been neglected, as well as the deformation of the steel block. The friction is minimized by greasing the surfaces of the specimen before testing. Qualitatively, the effect from the friction would generate a minor tendency to resist the free expansion in the fibre direction impeding the observed fracture. The fact that fracture did take place actually in the test suggested that the effect was not significant. The deformation of the fixture tended to undermine the magnitude of σ_3 and would promote premature failure. Again, given the fact that failure took place at much elevated stress level, this effect had not played a big part in the process.

Given the disparity between the two transverse compressive stresses not being as ideal as in the thought experiment, the UD cube responded to load in a manner described as follows. The stress went to a much higher level than the transverse compressive strength of the composite as obtained under uniaxial compression, as shown in Fig. 3(a) where the two cases are compared. The test under uniaxial compression had been conducted on the identical specimens as a reference. When such failure eventually happened, it was explosive. The remains of the specimen were very fragmented as shown in Fig 3(b). Tensile fibre fracture was obvious in support of the thought experiment. The matrix was subjected to triaxial compression and it was meant to be able to sustain a high stress level. The actual fracture of the matrix was the consequence of compressive stress wave in the fractured fibres reflected on the free surface to generate a tensile wave propagating inwards eventually meeting with that from the other side, causing a secondary tensile fracture in the matrix this time.

Turning a blind eye to the microscopic behavior as described above, the phenomenological observation was that the material failed over a cross-section on which the net macroscopic stresses, both direct and shear, vanish completely and yet failure took place. If the material failure is to be

determined by them, the strength would have to be zero, which was obviously not the case. One has to concede that, at least in this particular case, failure was not determined by the macroscopic stresses exposed on the fracture plane. This delivers the first exception.

Fig. 3: (a) Experimental stress-strain curves and (b) a tested fractured specimen

4 EXCEPTION 2

The second exception can be revealed in a special type of anisotropic composites where fibres are of elastic properties so low in comparison with those of the matrix that they could be considered as voids. These ‘fibres’ are unidirectionally aligned in the matrix. When such a ‘composite’ is uniaxially compressed in its transverse direction, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a), the microscopic stresses around a ‘fibre’ are readily obtained from a well-known problem of stress concentration around a circular hole in the theory of elasticity [9] as shown in Fig. 4(b) when the material is loaded in tension. The circumferential stress on the side is three times of the applied stress and of the same sense as the applied stress. A relatively minor observation is the circumferential stress at the both ends of the hole, which is at the same magnitude but of the opposite sense of the applied stress. When the applied stress is compressive, a brittle material may easily sustain the compressive stress three times of the applied stress on the sides of the hole. However, it could be vulnerable to resist the stress at the ends of the hole which is of the same magnitude of the applied stress but in tension. This is the mechanism of which advantages will be taken to facilitate the following TE.

Fig. 4: (a) UD fibre-weakened composite under uniaxial compression transverse to fibres, and (b) stress distribution around a circular hole in an isotropic sheet under uniaxial tension

4.1 Thought experiment 2: Uniaxial transverse compression to a UD fibre-weakened composite

Imagine a unidirectionally fibre-weakened composite as illustrated in Fig. 4(a) and subject it to uniaxial compression transverse to the ‘fibres’. Assume that the fibres were compliant enough to be

approximated as voids and that they were sparsely dispersed over the cross-section of the composite so that microscopic stress field around a hole is not affected by the presence of other holes. In this case, the stress distribution around a hole could be obtained from conventional theory of elasticity as the stress concentration problem for 2D stress states. When the material is under uniaxial compression, the direct stress on the top and at the bottom of the circular hole should be equal to the applied stress but in tension in the direction perpendicular to the applied stress and also to the axis of the fibres. On the side of the hole, there would be compressive stress of a magnitude of three times of the applied stress. Since the matrix was supposed to be so brittle that it was able to sustain a stress in compression at least three times of that in tension, the critical aspect would be fracture in tension starting from the left and right sides of any of the fibres. When it took place, fracture would be expected in the plane parallel to both the applied stress and the fibres. However, this particular plane is free from any macroscopic stresses. The same observation could be made as in the first TE, i.e. the macroscopic stresses on the fracture plane vanish completely. This provides yet another exception to Assumption F. Again, such UD fibre-weakened composites are not available. The closest physical resemblance will be pursued in the next subsection.

4.2 Physical experiments to resemble the idealisation in the above thought experiment

Untoughened crystal glass bricks with sparsely suspended bubbles in it are widely available, as shown in Fig. 5. They can be regarded as spherical particulate-weakened composites. The stress field is 3-dimensional with stress concentration characteristics similar to that in 2-dimensional case as shown in Fig. 4(b) although not to the exact numbers. With an isolated spherical hole in an isotropic material under uniaxial compression, biaxial tension is found on the poles of the hole whilst concentrated compression is along the equator of the hole [10], as a reasonable resemblance to the TE. To facilitate the experiment, the brick was water jet cut into $20 \times 20 \times 20$ mm cubes as the specimens to be tested, as shown in Fig. 6(a). They were compressed uniaxially with contact surfaces greased to minimize the effect of friction.

Fig. 5 An untoughened crystal glass brick with sparsely suspended bubbles

As expected, fracture took place on planes parallel to the direction of loading. As the material is macroscopically isotropic, there is no preferred plane parallel to the loading direction for the specimen to fracture and hence the material selected the plane to suit itself. However, they all appear to be parallel to the loading direction as can be seen in Fig. 6(b). On any of these planes as the fracture plane, the macroscopic stresses vanish and the failure in this particular case again has nothing to do with the macroscopic stresses exposed on the fracture plane. The strength of the material was definitely not zero and the experimentally recorded stress-displacement curves for some of the specimens tested are shown in Fig. 7 where the curves had been artificially shifted sideways to avoid overlapping. The stresses had in fact gone to rather high levels as shown there due to the brittle nature of the material.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6: Cubic glass specimens with dispersed bubbles (a) before testing (b) after testing (loaded in uniaxial compression vertically)

Fig. 7: Experimental stress-strain curves for a sample range of specimens

Samples with visible dispersed bubbles were employed above to make the point obvious. In reality, visual bubbles are not necessary. Clear specimens without any bubbles visible by naked eye were also tested, giving the similar behaviour as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Clear cubic glass specimens (a) before testing (b) after testing (side view, loaded in uniaxial compression vertically) and (c) top view

In both cases, fracture planes parallel to the loading direction were observed consistently, on which macroscopic stresses vanish. In other words, the stresses exposed on the fracture plane cannot be the reason for the fracture because these stresses are all zero. This produced yet another exception to Assumption F.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The assumption that failure is determined by the stresses exposed on the fracture plane is under scrutiny in this paper, whilst remaining in the realm of a phenomenological approach, although every material failure always has its microscopic reasons in depth. The assumption was fairly established as a part of the Mohr criterion for brittle, homogenous and isotropic materials. However, it has been argued to be inapplicable in general to heterogeneous and/or anisotropic materials. To reinforce the argument, two exceptions have been shown in which the assumption fell apart completely. In each case, a thought experiment was presented to have a neat and ideal scenario and it was then followed by a physical test in close resemblance to the respect thought experiment. Excellent agreements have been demonstrated between the thought experiments and their physical resemblances and both cases the fracture plane was free from macroscopic stresses contradicting the assumption that failure is determined by the stresses exposed on the fracture pane. Calling this assumption as ‘physically based’ or ‘physically sound’ is neither truthful nor responsible. As a consequence, it has misled the community developing failure criteria for composites profoundly. It is now the time to ditch it as the assumption should not have been made to composites in first place. Any hope of break-through leading to a consistent and reliable composite failure criterion demands fresh thinking.

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